

Quelques mots-clés

Savoirs Tacite	Expertise	Sciences des pratiques
Tacit knowledge	Beer-mat expertise	Practice turn
Explicit knowledge	Primary source knowledge	Ethnométhodologie
Knowledge management	Interactional expertise	
Affordance	Contributory expertise	
Relational tacit knowledge		
Somatic tacit knowledge		
Collective tacit knowledge		